

Sulphation of Jute Cellulose

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Sulphation of purified jute cellulose with chlorosulphonic acid, pyridine-SO₃ complex and concentrated sulphuric acid in the presence of different diluents were studied. Concentrated sulphuric acid in the presence of *n*-butyl alcohol along with some added water gave the best results when the reactions were carried out at 7° for 45 min. The effect of varying amounts of added water was studied, and the maximum sulphation was obtained with a cellulose/water ratio of 1 : 1. The product was white, semi-crystalline and soluble in water and had a degree of substitution of 2.0.

INTEREST¹ in the studies of natural and synthetic sulphated polysaccharides has grown tremendously these days due to the usefulness of these materials in the treatment of lipemic and thrombotic diseases. Braconnot¹ dissolved linen in cold concentrated sulphuric acid and obtained what he called, "*acide vigito sulphurique*". Later, analyses by a number of workers²⁻⁴ showed that the acid was a highly degraded cellulose sulphate. Since then various reports of preparing cellulose sulphate* by using sulphuric acid alone^{5,6} or in admixture with ammonium sulphate⁷ in the presence of inert diluents like toluene and benzene⁷, ethylene dichloride⁸ and aliphatic alcohols⁹, have appeared. Use of added water has also been mentioned.¹⁰

Cellulose sulphate has also been prepared by the use of the complexes formed by sulphur trioxide with such nucleophilic reagents as trimethylamine¹¹, triethylamine¹², poly(2-vinyl pyridine)¹³, pyridine¹⁴, *N,N*-dimethylformamide¹⁵ and dimethylsulphoxide¹⁶.

Although other reagents have been developed, sulphuric acid still remains⁶ as one of the major sulphating agent. Chlorosulphonic acid¹⁷ and pyridine or formamide^{18,19} have also been used for the sulphation of cellulose. Complete sulphation (D.S. 3.0) is not usually obtained. Degree of substitution (D.S.) between 1.0 and 2.0 has been reported by various workers for cellulose sulphate obtained from cotton and pulp. Only one report²⁰ is available where a D.S. of about 3.0 has been claimed.

Although jute contains more cellulose percentwise than wood, it is the wood pulp which is almost exclusively employed for the production of cellulose derivatives and jute has not been used at all. Recent researches in this laboratory have shown that the purified jute cellulose can be satisfactorily utilized for the preparation of sodium²¹ and potassium²² carboxymethylcellulose, cellulose phosphate²³ and cellulose nitrate²⁴. In continuation of these works it was thought worthwhile to investigate the sulphation of jute cellulose. Different sulphating agents

like chlorosulphonic acid, pyridine-sulphur trioxide complex and sulphuric acid in the presence of suitable diluents were used for sulphation with a view to finding out a suitable method for the preparation of cellulose sulphate from jute cellulose with a high degree of sulphation.

Experimental

Preparation of jute cellulose: Powdered jute was thoroughly boiled with sufficient 1% aqueous sodium hydroxide solution, washed with water, treated first with gaseous chlorine and then with aqueous alkaline sodium sulphite solution. The white cellulose thus obtained was washed thoroughly with water and dried.

Determination of sulphur content and D.S: Sulphur content of the sulphated polysaccharide was determined by digestion with perchloric acid in the presence of magnesium chloride or oxide. The acid was evaporated and the residue was dissolved in dilute hydrochloric acid. The sulphate was precipitated with barium chloride solution and the sulphur was determined gravimetrically. Digestion with concentrated nitric or hydrochloric acid²⁵ gave almost identical results but the perchloric acid digestion was much simpler to handle and it took much shorter time. The degree of substitution (D.S.) was calculated from the sulphur content by means of the usual formula²⁵

$$D.S. = \frac{1.62 \times (\% \text{ of sulphur})}{32 - (1.02 \times \% \text{ of sulphur})}$$

Sulphation with chlorosulphonic acid: Pure jute cellulose (10 g) was stirred with chlorosulphonic acid (30 ml) and pyridine (300 ml) at 30° for 7 hr. The mixture was then diluted with rectified spirit, filtered, and washed several times with rectified spirit. Neutralization with aqueous ethanolic sodium hydroxide followed by washing with ethanol gave the sodium salt of cellulose sulphate which contained 15.6% sulphur corresponding to a D.S. of 1.56.

* Cellulose sulphate means the sodium salt.

The reaction was repeated with changes in the diluents, reaction time and temperature and the results are presented in Table 1.

TABLE 1—SULPHATION OF JUTE CELLULOSE WITH CHLOROSULPHONIC ACID AND PYRIDINE-SULPHUR TRIOXIDE COMPLEX

Sulphating agent	Temp. °C	Time	Reaction medium	D.S.
Chlorosulphonic acid	30	7 hr	Pyridine	1.56
"	85	7 hr	"	1.62
"	7	45 min	<i>n</i> -Butyl alcohol	1.40
"	30	6 hr	Pyridine + <i>n</i> -butyl alcohol	0.21
Pyridine-SO ₃ complex <i>in situ</i>	30	6 hr	Pyridine + chloroform	0.27
Pyridine-SO ₃ complex	30	6 hr	Excess pyridine	1.56
"	85	6 hr	"	0.75

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF DILUENTS ON SULPHATION WITH CONCENTRATED SULPHURIC ACID

Diluent	% of sulphur	D.S.	Solubility in water
Methyl alcohol	6.90	0.44	Dispersed
Ethyl alcohol	6.40	0.42	"
<i>iso</i> -Propyl alcohol	6.87	0.44	"
<i>n</i> -Propyl alcohol	15.57	1.56	Partly soluble
<i>n</i> -Butyl alcohol	17.36	2.00	Soluble
<i>iso</i> -Butyl alcohol	15.11	1.47	Partly soluble
<i>sec</i> -Butyl alcohol	13.74	1.23	"
<i>t</i> -Butyl alcohol	8.20	0.56	Dispersed
<i>n</i> -Pentyl alcohol	4.60	0.27	"

Sulphation with pyridine-sulphur trioxide complex: The title complex was prepared according to the method of Sisler and Andreith²⁶ by the action of dry pyridine and chlorosulphonic acid in chloroform at 0°. But contrary to the reported results²⁷, the complex prepared was not very stable and hence, either it was used immediately after preparation or was prepared *in situ*.

Pure jute cellulose (4 g) was added to a mixture of pyridine-sulphur trioxide complex (20 g) and pyridine (130 ml) with constant stirring. The reaction mixture was then stirred for 6 hr at 30°. Afterwards, the mixture was filtered and the cellulose sulphate was recovered by following the procedure described in the previous experiment. The product had a D.S. of 1.56. Repetition of the reaction at a higher temperature (85°) lowered the D.S. to 0.75 (Table 1). When a reaction was conducted with chlorosulphonic acid and pyridine in the presence of chloroform as a diluent (pyridine-sulphur trioxide complex *in situ*), the D.S. dropped to 0.27 only.

Sulphation with concentrated sulphuric acid in the presence of aliphatic alcohols and added water: Purified jute cellulose (10 g) was added to an ice-cold mixture of concentrated sulphuric acid (62 ml), water and a low molecular weight (1-5 carbon atom) aliphatic

alcohol (50 ml), stirred for the desired period of time at a selected temperature and the resulting cellulose sulphate was recovered following the procedure described earlier. Of all the alcohols used, *n*-butanol always gave the highest sulphation. Therefore, in further experiments, *n*-butanol was used as the reaction medium.

Several experiments were carried out with *n*-butanol as the diluent along with different amounts of added water. The results are presented in Table 3 and Fig. 1.

TABLE 3—EFFECT OF CELLULOSE/WATER RATIO ON THE D.S.

Water added (ml)	Cellulose/water ratio	% of sulphur	D.S.	Solubility in water
0	1 : 0	13.00	1.12	Dispersed
2	5 : 1	13.73	1.23	Almost soluble
6	5 : 3	15.20	1.50	"
10	1 : 1	17.36	2.00	Soluble
15	2 : 3	15.52	1.55	Partly soluble
20	1 : 2	7.30	0.48	Dispersed

Fig. 1. Effect of added water on the degree of sulphation.

In another experiment with 20 g cellulose, portions of the reaction mixture were withdrawn at definite intervals of time and the sulphated cellulose recovered and analysed to find out the progress of sulphation with time. The sulphur content and the D.S. of the products at different intervals of time are presented in Table 4 and Fig. 2.

TABLE 4—PROGRESS OF SULPHATION WITH TIME

Time	% of sulphur	D.S.	Solubility in water
5 min	4.57	0.27	Dispersed
15 min	13.28	1.16	Dispersed
30 min	15.00	1.46	Partly soluble
45 min	17.36	2.00	Soluble
1 hr	16.42	1.75	"
2½ hr	16.56	1.78	"
6 hr	16.60	1.79	"
22½ hr	16.47	1.76	"

Later, a set of experiments was carried out with *n*-butanol as the diluent and cellulose/water ratio of

Fig. 2. Progress of sulphation with time.

1:1 for 45 min at various reaction temperatures. The results are presented in Table 5 and Fig. 3.

TABLE 5—SULPHATION AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES

Temp. °C	% of sulphur	D.S.	Solubility in water
-7	6.86	0.44	Dispersed
0	13.50	1.20	Partly soluble
7	17.36	2.00	Soluble
14	15.10	1.46	Partly soluble
32	6.34	0.40	Dispersed
50	7.21	0.47	"

Fig. 3. Effect of temperature on the degree of sulphation.

Results and Discussion

Sulphation of jute cellulose with chlorosulphonic acid and pyridine gave partially water soluble cellulose sulphate with a D.S. of 1.56. Attempts to improve on the product by varying the reaction parameters only improved the D.S. slightly (to 1.62 at 85°; Table 1). Interestingly, when chloroform and pyridine were used as the reaction medium along

with chlorosulphonic acid, a very low D.S. (0.27) was obtained. However, when pyridine-SO₃ complex was prepared beforehand and was used as the sulphating agent in chloroform medium, cellulose sulphate with a much higher D.S. was obtained (Table 1). Probably, the pyridinium chloride, which is said²⁸ to have detrimental effects on sulphation, was responsible for the low D.S. in the previous case.

Sulphation was, then, carried out with concentrated sulphuric acid in the presence of various alcohols^{9,29} with small amounts of added water. From the results presented in Table 2, it may be seen that with methyl, ethyl and *iso*-propyl alcohols, a very low D.S. was attained, but with *n*-propyl alcohol a sudden rise in the D.S. was observed and the highest sulphation (D.S. 2.00) was achieved with *n*-butanol as the diluent. The product in the last case was also completely soluble in water. *iso*-Butyl alcohol gave a lower D.S. (1.47) and the esterification decreased rapidly with the use of *sec*-butyl, *t*-butyl and amyl alcohols in that order. The low sulphation with the lower alcohols may be attributed to the high solubility of water in the lower alcohols and the penetration of the lower alcohols into the amorphous region of the cellulose moiety and thereby competing with it for sulphation. The decrease in the D.S. with higher alcohols may be due to the heterogeneous nature of the reaction medium. The complete mechanism is, however, not well understood.

It may be seen from Table 3 and Fig. 1 that the D.S. steadily increased with the increase of added water upto a water/cellulose ratio of 1:1, but decreased sharply afterwards. The maximum sulphation was obtained with a cellulose/water ratio of 1:1. Water acts mainly as a swelling agent as in the carboxymethylation of jute cellulose in alcoholic medium²¹, and presumably, an optimum swelling is attained with a cellulose/water ratio of 1:1. With larger proportions of added water, the dilution of the sulphuric acid probably decreases its efficiency as the sulphating agent.

From a study of the progress of sulphation with time, it was found that the sulphation was rapid in the first fifteen minutes and was virtually complete within 45 min (Table 4), and after that time there was a slight decrease in the D.S. (Fig. 2.), due probably to some concurrent desulphation by hydrolysis. Afterwards, there was no significant change in the D.S. even when the reaction was continued for more than 22 hr.

Table 5 and Fig. 3 show the temperature dependence of the sulphation reaction. It was observed that the sulphation was slow at temperatures below 0°. Highest sulphation took place when the reaction was carried out at about 7°. Higher temperatures lowered the degree of sulphation, the reasons for which are not very clear.

The cellulose sulphate (sodium salt) prepared at optimum conditions with sulphuric acid from jute cellulose with a D.S. of 2.0 was completely soluble in water and a 1% solution had a viscosity of 14 mp. Cellulose sulphates with D.S. 1.6-1.9 were almost completely soluble in water with small amounts of

dispersed particles, those with D.S. 1.0-1.6 were partially soluble, and others dispersed only. The soluble cellulose sulphate and those with D.S. 1.6-1.9 were obtained in solid lumps, others were fibrous. All the products were white in colour.

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